

Nursery (UBN) screening technique was used and disease rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)*.

Scores indicated the dominance of

susceptibility over resistance (see table). The high heterosis for leaf and neck BL resistance in TKM9/IR50 and its reciprocal shows that these two parents may have complementary

genes although they are individually susceptible. TKM9/Co 29 and its reciprocal were susceptible to both leaf and neck BL. □

Tolerance of Sitopas crosses for ragged stunt virus (RSV)

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Sitopas, an Indonesian variety, has been reported as susceptible to but tolerant of RSV. Crosses were made to transfer its resistance to IR varieties and lines.

We evaluated 523 F₃ lines from 5 crosses of Sitopas and 3 IR varieties and lines: IR20, susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH) and intolerant of RSV; IR8234-OT-9-2, resistant to BPH biotype 1 but intolerant of RSV; and sitopas, tolerant of RSV but susceptible to BPH biotype 1.

Seeds were soaked in petri dishes in five batches mid-Jun to late Aug. Germinating seeds were transplanted in clay pots. Seedlings were artificially inoculated with RSV at 11 d by the standard mass screening method in the greenhouse. Seedlings infected with RSV were transplanted in the field at 45 d from early Aug to early Oct.

Reaction of rice varieties and Sitopas progenies to RSV. IRRI, 1985.

Designation	Plots (%) with \geq 50% fertility	Mean fertility ^a
Sitopas (check)	61.2	39.1 a
IR43301 (Sitopas//IR26702-52-3)	12.2	15.8 b
IR46641 (Sitopas//IR26702-52-3//IR8234-OT-9-2)	15.3	13.3 b
IR46630 (IR20/Sitopas//BR118-3B-17)	7.6	8.1 c
IR46733 (IR20/Sitopas//BR51-91-7)	4.2	2.8 d
IR46734 (IR20/Sitopas//New Sabarmati)	4.1	3.1 d
IR8234-OT-9-2 (check)	2.8	2.8 d
IR20 (check)	0.6	1.3 d

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Spacing was 30 cm between rows with 25 cm between plants, in a randomized complete block design with 2 replications. N at 100 kg/ha was applied in 2 splits. Spikelet fertility was used to evaluate level of tolerance for RSV.

Sitopas confirmed its tolerance.

IR20 and IR8234-OT-9-2 were intolerant. Crosses with IR43301 and IR46641 showed significant numbers of fertile plants (see table). They also had more plots with at least 50% fertility, showing that Sitopas was able to transmit its tolerance for RSV into some of its progeny. □

Sources of resistance to sheath rot (ShR)

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During 1985-86 thaladi season, 59 rice cultures were screened for resistance to ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw.) Gams. under field conditions where disease pressure was very high. Nine cultures showed high resistance (see table). □

Resistance of rice cultures to ShR, 1985-86. Aduthurai, India.

Culture	Cross	Disease index ^a	Disease reaction ^a
Manoharasali	Donor	1	HR
RB2069-2-6-1	Swarnadhan/Andrewsali	1	HR
RP2071-18-1-1	Swarnadhan/NLR9674	1	HR
CR331-1-1-3	Jagannath/Mashuri	1	HR
IR9202-21-1	IR2053-521-1-1-K 116/KN-1B-361-1-8-6-9	1	HR
RP1057-35-1-1	KN-1B-361-1-8-6-9 RP 5-32/Pankaj	1	HR
VRS286-4-1	—	1	HR
VRS163-2-2-2-3	—	1	HR
ARC14529	—	1	HR
IET85 84	IET4141/CR98-7216	1	HR
TN1	—	7	HS
IET7575	Sona/Manoharsali	9	HS
IET4 141	RP29 1 /IR22	9	HS

^a Standard evaluation system for rice 1-9 scale. ^bHR = highly resistant, HS = highly susceptible.